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Studies On The Individual And Combined Effects Of Thyroid And Pituitary Hormones On Post-Embryonic Development In *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.)

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Abstract

This study is focus on the Thyroid and Pituitary hormone treatment (individual and combined) given to the newly hatched larvae of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for about one month and revealed faster post-embryonic development which is correlated with growth, development, length-weight relationship and condition factor as against the control experiments. The larvae exposed to individual hormones doses T1=75 mg/lit. dose of thyroid hormone, P2=2mg/lit. dose of pituitary hormone and combined (Thyroid and Pituitary) hormone doses T2P2=100+2mg/lit. proved suitable in all respect. Mortality figure comes out 4,5,7 and 12 for 0.0mg/lit, 75mg/lit.,100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit. dose individual thyroid hormone treatment ; 4,5,7 and 11 for 0.0mg/lit, 1mg/lit.,2mg/lit. and 3mg/lit. dose pituitary hormone treatment and 4, 6, 5 and 10 for 0+0mg/lit., 75+1mg/lit.,100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. dose treatment respectively. The study revealed that there was a close relationship between growth and development. There is a very important aspect of morphometrical parameters showed marked changes in all individual and combined (Thyroid and Pituitary hormone) treated experiment (Cultural investigation). These observations suggest that most powerful hormone therapy may have prove in the practical utility in the hatchery reared culture of freshwater Indian major carps, *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.).

Keywords

Thyroid hormone, Pituitary hormone, post-embryonic development, length-weight relationship, Condition Factor (K), *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.).

Introduction

Thyroid hormone plays an important role on growth and protein metabolism of all vertebrates. The phase of metabolism that promotes post-embryonic development, growth along with protein synthesis, by target growth cell is also one among the other descriptions of thyroid hormone application activity. The effect of thyroid treatment on the post-embryonic development of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) is not yet fully known and needs further investigation.

With the view point in the present communication an effort is made to work out the optimum dose of hormone which could be able to affect some aspects of post-embryonic development in a positive direction, as thyroid hormone treatment has been shown to promote post-embryonic development, growth ,condition factor and survival in several fish species.

Pituitary hormone plays an important role in the maturation of gonads and body growth of fish. The growth hormone (Somatotropin) of the pituitary gland also influences protein, carbohydrate and fate metabolism to a great extent (Knobil et. al.,(1957). The effect of pituitary hormone treatment on the post-embryonic development of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) is not yet fully known and needs further investigation.

The thyroid and pituitary hormone have been known as the most important biochemical substances, which are responsible for metamorphic differentiation during larval development period along with many physiological process of prime importance (Belsare et. al;1966).

The maintenance of adequate balance of thyroid and pituitary hormone levels are important prerequisite for proper management of reproductive biology, development,

growth and its may prove important regulating factor. The effect of thyroid hormone treatment along with the pituitary in a combined form on post- embryonic development of *Cirrhina mrigala* is not fully clear and needs further investigation. With this view point in the present study, an effort has been made to work out the optimum combined dose of thyroid and pituitary hormones which could be able to affect some aspects of post-embryonic development in a positive direction.

In fishery science, the knowledge on the length- weight of fish has a vital importance, as it is not only helps to establish the mathematical relationship between the two variables-the length and weight, but also to convert one variable into another. The body parameter of a fish continually changes with ageing. The weight of a fish is a function of its length (Hile,1936). The length-weight relationship can be used to express the relative health, robustness and therefore, the economic value of the fish. The value of condition factor is useful in explaining differences among individuals of the same length. Condition factor or ponderal index or more popularly known K factor is another important derivative of growth.

Objective of study

This study is focus on the Thyroid and Pituitary hormone treatment (individual and combined) given to the newly hatched larvae of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for about one month and revealed faster post-embryonic development which is correlated with growth, development, length-weight relationship and condition factor as against the control experiments.

Review of Literature

Some of the important contributions on the said field of studies are from Land grebe, *et.al.*(1941); Baldwin, *et.al.*(1942); Swift,D.R. (1954); Hoar, *et. al.* (1955); Knobil, *et.al.* (1957); Lostroh, *et.al.* (1958); Atz *et. al.*(1959) Scow, R. O.; (1959); Ali, M.A.; (1961); Sneed, *et. al.* (1961) Das, *et. al.*(1962); Nicall, *et. al.* (1965); Belsare, *et. al.*(1966) Tata,J.R. (1968); Liley, *et.al.*(1969); Yamazaki, *et.al.* (1976); Clarke, *et.al.*(1977); Holde, *et. al.* (1980); Wilson, *et. al.*(1980); Adelman,*et.al.* (1982) Miwa, *et. al.* (1985); Joss, J.M.P.;(1985); Mchean, *et. al.*(1990); Brown, *et.al.*(1995); Lakra, *et. al.*(1996); Tay *et. al.* (1997); Brzuska *et. al.* (1999); Roy *et. al.* (2000); Blanton, *et. al.* (2007); Arjona *et. al.* (2011); *Chang et. al.* (2012); Hamed, *et.al.*(2018); Soheil Alinezhad, *et. al.* (2020); Islam, *et. al.*(2021); Hasan, *et.al.* (2021); and Romain, *et.al.*(2022).

Methodology

The newly hatched larvae (3-4 days old) of *Cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) were collected from fish farm in the close vicinity of Raebareli. The hatchlings for consecutive development stages were brought to laboratory and transferred to plastic trough under observation. In each experimental trough, 20 specimens were placed on the basis of proper stocking density (Approximately 2 fish /lit.). The physio- chemical conditions of the experimental troughs were maintained merely natural by the use of sand particles, hydrilla plant, zoo and phytoplanktons. Hitachi readymade food pellets in quantity were also given at regular intervals to all the experimental larvae. The individual thyroid hormone (Proloid 0.15mg thyroxine) doses of 75mg/lit., 100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit.; pituitary hormone doses of 1mg/lit, 2mg/lit. and 3mg/lit and combined (thyroid and pituitary) hormone doses 0+0mg/lit., 75+1mg/lit.,100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. concentration were prepared by pituitary extract alcoholic method from the common carp and in each trough one kind of them was added. By random sampling five specimens from each kind of experiment and control were taken out for derivation of mean standard under different aspects of studies on post- embryonic development at a successive time period 30 days in order to study later developmental stages. Morpho-metrical parameters of the larvae were recorded with the help of Vernier Calipers and weighing balance machine at the end of the experiments.

Various parameters related to the post embryonic development, growth and condition factor or length-weight relationship relevance's were calculated on the basis of the following equation:-

$$K = \frac{W \times 10^5}{L^3}$$

Where, K =Condition factor

W = weight of fish

L = Length Of fish

10^5 = Bringing the Condition factor (K) near the unit (Carlander, 1970)

Result and Discussion

Individual Dose Treatment (Thyroid Hormone)

On the perusal of the parameters indicated in the Table 1, it can be concluded that a dose 75mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 1, 2 &Table 1).

Table-1

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	75mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	100mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	125mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.024	32.177 \pm 0.840	27.002 \pm 0.493	27.260 \pm 0.565
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.005	19.322 \pm 0.627	16.707 \pm 0.476	16.043 \pm 0.482
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.018	08.307 \pm 0.233	06.767 \pm 0.313	06.532 \pm 0.441
4	Caudal fin length	02.360 \pm 0.278	02.668 \pm 0.373	02.560 \pm 0.422	02.572 \pm 0.272
5	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.054	06.477 \pm 0.507	05.777 \pm 0.479	06.317 \pm 0.523
6	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.037	09.282 \pm 0.508	07.847 \pm 0.666	07.232 \pm 0.484
7	Body Weight	88.876 \pm 0.486	114.837 \pm 0.493	110.320 \pm 0.289	111.896 \pm 0.495
8	Condition factor	00.845	00.344	00.560	00.551
9	Mortality	Four	Five	Seven	Twelve

The general morpho-metrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae revealed that a dose of 75mg/lit., standard length 32.177mm; body length 19.322mm; head length 08.307mm; caudal fin length 02.668; height of the body at anal fin base 06.477mm; height of the body at dorsal fin base 09.282mm; and body weight 114.837mg was observed, which is significant, in terms of the best estimated post-embryonic development.

It has also been marked those early developmental periods when morphogenesis is on it full seeing, the thyroid hormone treatment resulted into maximum increment in standard body length at 75mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 75mg/lit; 100mg/lit. and 125mg/lit. dose treatment (Table1)

The application of T1 (75mg/lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment prove to be the best in term of total length in comparison to control and other thyroid hormone doses.

Condition factor is calculated for different doses of thyroid hormone treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 2 the Condition factor showed decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of minimum Condition factor at T1(75mg/lit.) provide the values as 00.344 for 30 days experiment.

Therefore, 75mg/lit. dose was calculated to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

Individual Dose Treatment (Pituitary Hormone)

On the behalf of our experiment the parameters shown in the Table 2, it can be concluded that a dose 2mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 3,4 &Table 2).

Table-2

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	1mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	2mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	3mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.048	23.712 \pm 0.050	30.867 \pm 0.119	30.067 \pm 0.039
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.010	14.507 \pm 0.379	19.847 \pm 0.045	19.067 \pm 0.039
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.036	06.857 \pm 0.057	07.392 \pm 0.094	07.067 \pm 0.039
4	Caudal fin length	2.360 \pm 0.278	2.398 \pm 0.441	2.502 \pm 0.107	2.438 \pm 0.375
5	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.109	05.432 \pm 0.150	06.437 \pm 0.088	06.262 \pm 0.037
6	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.074	06.747 \pm 0.105	08.832 \pm 0.035	08.362 \pm 0.083
7	Body Weight	88.867	106.392	109.867	107.378
8	Condition Factor	0.845	0.797	0.373	0.394
9	Mortality	Four	Five	Seven	Eleven

The general morpho-metrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae revealed that a dose of 2mg/lit., standard length 30.867mm; body length 19.847mm; head length 7.392mm; Caudal fin length 2.502mm; Height of the body at anal fin base 6.437mm; Height of the body at dorsal fin base 8.832mm and body weight 109.867mg was observed, which is significant, for post-embryonic development.

These results are also more significant for early developmental periods when morphogenesis is on its full swing and the pituitary treatment resulted into maximum increment in standard body length at 2mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 1mg/lit; 2mg/lit. and 3mg/lit. dose treatment (Table 2)

The application of P2 (2mg/Lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment proved to be the best in terms of total length in comparison to control and other pituitary doses.

Further, Condition factor is calculated for different doses of pituitary hormone in treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 2 the condition factor showed a decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of minimum condition factor at P1 (1mg/lit.) provided the values as 0.797 for 30 days experiment.

According experimental values, 2mg/lit. dose was observed to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

Combined Doses Treatment (Thyroid+Pituitary)

According to our experimental values indicated in the Table 3, it can be concluded that a dose 100+2mg/lit. proved to be the best in term of post-embryonic development (Fig. 5,6 & Table 3).

Table 3: Morphometry of *cirrhina mrigala* (Ham.) larvae treated with combined doses of thyroid (T) and pituitary (P) hormone (mg/lit.).

S.No.	General Measurement	000mg/lit. (Average in mean \pm S.D)	75+1mg/lit.(T1+P1) (Average in mean \pm S.D)	100+2mg/lit.(T2+P2) (Average in mean \pm S.D)	125+3mg/lit (T3+P3). (Average in mean \pm S.D)
1	Standard Length	21.897 \pm 0.048	33.247 \pm 1.564	37.535 \pm 1.533	37.067 \pm 1.337
2	Body Length	13.397 \pm 0.010	22.242 \pm 0.892	25.295 \pm 1.652	25.660 \pm 0.843
3	Head Length	06.307 \pm 0.036	08.322 \pm 0.867	09.562 \pm 0.907	08.55 \pm 1.843
4	Caudal fin length	2.360 \pm 0.278	2.720 \pm 0.198	2.803 \pm 0.403	2.730 \pm 0.371
5	Height of the body at anal fin base	04.887 \pm 0.109	07.222 \pm 0.925	07.617 \pm 1.091	07.522 \pm 0.659
6	Height of the body at dorsal fin base	06.747 \pm 0.074	09.405 \pm 0.965	09.690 \pm 0.818	08.240 \pm 1.305
7	Body Weight	88.876 \pm 0.486	118.068 \pm 0.363	120.126 \pm 0.244	119.962 \pm 0.128
8	Condition factor	0.846	0.321	0.227	0.235
9	Mortality	Four	six	five	Ten

The morphometrical parameters of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham) larvae shows that a dose of 100+2mg/lit., revealed experimental values of standard length 37.535mm; body length 25.295mm; head length 9.562mm; Caudal fin length 2.803mm; height of the body at anal fin base 7.617mm; height of the body at dorsal fin base 9.690mm; and body weight 120.126mg was observed , which is significant in terms of the best estimated in correspondence to post-embryonic development.

These parameters indicate that during developmental periods when morphogenesis is on its full swing, the combined thyroid and pituitary hormone treatment gives maximum results in accordance standard body length at 100+2mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 75+1mg/lit; 100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. dose treatment (Table3)

Thus the newly hatched larvae during developmental periods when morphogenesis is on its full swing with the combined thyroid and pituitary hormone treatment resulted into

maximum increment in standard body length at 100+2mg/lit. dose. Survival percentage was maximum in control which gradually decreased at 75+1mg/lit; 100+2mg/lit. and 125+3mg/lit. dose treatment (Table3)

The application of T2P2 (100+2mg/Lit.) for 30 days duration of the experiment prove to be the best in term of total length in comparison to control and other combined thyroid and pituitary hormone doses.

Condition factor is also calculated for different doses of combined thyroid and pituitary hormone in treatment of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) for 30 days experiment. As Fig. 6 the condition factor showed decrement in respect to control sets. The best result in terms of minimum condition factor at T2 P2(100+2mg/lit.) shows the value as 0.227 for 30 days experiment.

Therefore, 100+2mg/lit. dose was calculated to be the best effective dose in respect to post-embryonic development and low mortality of *Cirrhina Mrigala* (Ham.) larvae.

Conclusion

A review of all the experiments conducted with individually and combined doses of thyroid and pituitary has revealed that hormonal treatment to developing newly hatched larvae resulted enhanced growth and morphogenesis as compared to control in all sets of experiments. The effectiveness of the dose varies with the quantity and duration of the respective hormonal treatment. Among the different dose treatments T1(75mg/lit.), P2(2mg/lit.) and T2P2(100mg/lit.+2mg/lit.) were found more effective to their respective categories, but T2P2 dose treatment resulted further better results in contrast to control, T1, and P2 dose treatments.

In terms of length-weight relationship or condition factor of individual T1(75mg/lit.), P2(2mg/lit.) and combined T2P2(100mg/lit.+2mg/lit.) doses of thyroid and pituitary hormone respectively a gradual decrement was observed in comparison to control.

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